

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Fluorescence Quenching of Dimethylaminonaphthalene Dyes Badan and Prodan by Tryptophan in Cytochromes P450 and Micelles

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Figure S1. Stationary fluorescence spectra of Badan labeled CYPs: CYP102-Trp (in black), CYP102-His (in red), CYP119-His (in blue), CYP119-Trp (in magenta). Excited at 370 nm.

Figure S2. Left: Stationary fluorescence spectra of Badan in Brij[®] 58 micelles measured at different Trp concentrations (black) and Badan spectrum in pure Tris buffer (red). Right: Stationary fluorescence spectra of Prodan in Brij[®] 58 micelles measured at different Trp concentrations. Excited at 370 nm.

Figure S3. Area-normalized Badan fluorescence spectra in Brij[®] 58 micelles as a function on Trp concentration in the 0 – 20 mM range. Excited at 370 nm.

Table S1. Badan fluorescence lifetime quenching by tryptophan in Brij[®] 58 micellar solution. (Measured at 550 nm. Values are based on single-exponential fitting of fluorescence decay.)

[Trp] (mM)	Lifetime (ns)	SV ratio τ_0/τ
0.0	2.64	1
2.4	2.62	1.008
4.9	2.60	1.015
7.3	2.60	1.018
9.9	2.54	1.039
12.1	2.51	1.050
14.7	2.48	1.065
17.2	2.46	1.072
19.6	2.43	1.088

Table S2. Prodan fluorescence lifetime quenching by tryptophan in Brij[®] 58 micellar solution. (Measured at 550 nm. Values are based on double-exponential fitting of fluorescence decay.)

[Trp] (mM)	Lifetimes (ns)		Amplitudes (relative)		Average lifetime	SV ratio $\tau_{dec,0}/\tau_{dec}$
	τ_{rise}	τ_{decay}	B_{rise}	B_{decay}		
0.0	0.55	3.56	-10.4	110.4	3.87	1.000
7.9	0.55	3.51	-10.1	110.1	3.81	1.016
15.3	0.52	3.42	-9.75	109.8	3.70	1.048
22.3	0.49	3.38	-9.07	109.1	3.64	1.065
28.8	0.46	3.32	-8.12	108.1	3.55	1.091
35.0	0.44	3.28	-8.17	108.2	3.51	1.104
40.8	0.43	3.25	-7.74	107.7	3.47	1.117
46.4	0.43	3.21	-7.56	107.6	3.42	1.133
51.6	0.46	3.15	-7.69	107.7	3.35	1.156
61.3	0.43	3.11	-7.28	107.3	3.30	1.172
70.0	0.42	3.06	-6.70	106.7	3.24	1.197
85.3	0.38	3.00	-5.40	105.4	3.14	1.232
98.0	0.37	2.97	-4.42	104.4	3.08	1.257
108.9	0.35	2.89	-2.90	102.9	2.96	1.309
118.3	0.35	2.86	-2.70	102.7	2.93	1.323